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LALINET EarthCARE CAL/VAL ACTIVITIES

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The Latin America Lidar Network EarthCARE Cal/Val Activities proposal aims to expand the number of institutions and collaborations to foster regional integration of EarthCARE-related measurements and datasets. This initiative seeks to provide well-organized EarthCARE Cal/Val datasets by establishing an alliance of partners from South America, Europe, and South Africa. The primary objective is to conduct campaigns and establish validation teams in the region, enabling a deeper exploration of science themes that sit at the core of EarthCARE mission.

The scientific goals of this initiative include, but are not limited to, investigating: (1) the long-range transport of biomass-burning plumes from South America to Africa, (2) the impacts of the South Atlantic Anomaly on data quality, (3) the troposphere-stratosphere-mesosphere coupling in the Southern Hemisphere, and (4) data harmonization. These goals will be translated into work packages (WPs) involving coordinated measurements through field campaigns in Brazil and with our international partners.

To support these campaigns, we aim to improve local capabilities under the EarthCARE Level 2 A products protocol. The proposal timeline aligns well with EarthCARE activities, with an 18-month preparation phase before the launch scheduled for the first semester of 2024, followed by 18 months of validation activities. This effort is expected to yield several sub-products that will foster synergy among active research groups in South America, with potential expansion to broader regions in the Southern Hemisphere.

As an ultimate goal, we aspire to conduct a coordinated harmonization campaign in collaboration with European groups and other networks, such as EARLINET. The Latin America Lidar Network EarthCARE Cal/Val Activities proposal represents an important step towards enhanced regional integration and scientific advancements in the field of lidar measurements and related datasets.